

THE CARBON FOAM WITH SKELETON STRUCTURE IN COMPOSITE MATERIALS

J. Myalski¹, B. Hekner², A. Posmyk³,

¹Faculty of Materials Engineering and Metallurgy, Silesian University of Technology,
Katowice, 40-019, Krasińskiego 8, Poland
Email: Jerzy.Myalski@polsl.pl, web page: <http://www.polsl.pl>

²Faculty of Materials Engineering and Metallurgy, Silesian University of Technology,
Katowice, 40-019, Krasińskiego 8, Poland
Email: Bartosz.Hekner@polsl.pl, web page: <http://www.polsl.pl>

³Faculty of Transport, Silesian University of Technology,
Katowice, 40-019, Krasińskiego 8, Poland
Email: Andrzej.Posmyk@polsl.pl, web page: <http://www.polsl.pl>

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ABSTRACT

This article presents results for composite materials with three different types of foams reinforcement. The foams were made by aluminum oxide, aluminum oxide covered by glassy carbon and only glassy carbon material. Applied structures of foams were characterized by high porosity, what gave an opportunity to infiltration by melted metal. An aluminum casting alloy was used as a matrix. Due to foam structure application, a mass decreasing, strength properties increasing, increasing of maximum load and temperature of friction point were possible. Moreover, the foams reinforcement provide uniform distribution of reinforcement phase. The typical problems in classical casting technology like segregation and sedimentation can be avoided also. However, the most important point was possibility of tribological properties correction. Especially, the application of glassy carbon material resulted in tribological properties increasing. In case of reinforcement Al₂O₃+GC, the glassy carbon led to friction coefficient decreasing and to limitation of wear. The small particles of glassy carbon, formed as a result wear destruction of foam or coating layer, were playing a role of solid lubricant between friction couple materials. The glassy carbon particles resulted in decreasing of friction coefficient up to typical value for sliding materials. In case of material reinforced by aluminum oxide foam, the friction coefficient value was as high as in typical friction materials. These results ensure high potential of application of presented materials.

1 INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the composite materials displace a classic materials in many field of industry, like aerospace or automotive industry. The synergic actions of each component of composite give an opportunity to achieve unique final properties [1]. One of the most common materials hybrids are the metal- ceramic composites. High plasticity and thermal conductivity of metal are combined with high hardness and thermal stabilisation of ceramic [2, 3]. However, a proper bonding between phases of composite causes many technological problems. The first tries of manufacturing of this material type based on introduction of ceramic particles into the melted metal matrix [4, 5]. However, obtained materials revealed many defects. The differences in density between components led to sedimentation of ceramic phase in volume of composite. Moreover, the problems with clusters and agglomeration were also observed. As a try of limit those problems, the stirring of the melted matrix during particles introducing was used [5, 6]. This method caused reduction of materials defects, but the investments on the energy and stirrer material were needed. Another idea relied on totally changing of manufacturing process. The powder metallurgy was applied for manufacturing composite materials [2, 7-9].

A possibility of proper bonding between phases was one of the most important benefits of this method, because it is not possible using classic method. However, the powder metallurgy method required complex technological process, frequently consist of a few steps. The literature data analysis and own experience revealed that for proper bonding between components, the additional milling before sintering process is required [2, 7-10]. It multiplied an investments and a time of production. Moreover, the application of milling process in industrial conditions was particularly difficult due to low effectiveness.

This article present new idea of manufacturing of high quality composite material using simply technique. The presented research base on application of spatial ceramic foam as a reinforcement of metal – ceramic materials producing by infiltration method [11, 12]. The skeleton reinforcement give an opportunity to eliminate all typical problems observed in casting method. Due to using a reinforcement in a form of foams, the perfect uniform distribution of reinforcement can be achieved [13]. Moreover, this technique allows to use reinforcement material only in required areas. It causes reduction of mass and cost of final element at the same time. The next important benefits of this technique is its simplicity. The reinforced foam can be infiltrated by liquid metal, what do not require high advanced technology. Moreover, the quality of bonding between phases seems to be not as important as in classic material. Because of interpenetration between metal and ceramic, the reinforcement phase is not exposed to pulling out from the matrix.

The another benefit of presented solutions is a possibility of obtain different properties using various materials of reinforcement. Using adequate technique, it is possible to manufacturing a spatial structures made by aluminum oxide, silicon carbide, glassy carbon or another ceramic materials. The application of hard ceramic (like Al_2O_3 or SiC) lead to increasing of psychical properties, especially hardness and compressive strength [14]. Moreover, those materials reveal high coefficient of friction (COF) in sliding applications. Typical ceramic materials revealed COF value higher than 0.3, what predestined it as a friction material with stable friction coefficient and low wear. However, the application of this type of particles could resulted in very high wear of coutermaterial, what in some cases of friction couples materials is unacceptable. The other type of applied ceramic – glassy carbon is characterized by high hardness and low shear modulus. This specific properties provide low coefficient of friction and low wear in sliding conditions. In friction point this material plays a role of solid lubricant because GC is smeared on the friction surface and make a protection against progressive wear [15-17]. The GC material reveal COF value much lower than 0.3, what is typical value for sliding material. It is obvious that a control of final material properties of metal matrix composite is possible due to application adequate amount of reinforcement phase. However, due to application of heterophase reinforcement, a full control of tribological properties using required thickness of GC phase is possible. Because of possibility of obtain wide range of properties using various amounts of phases, presented material solution seems to be especially most promising for developing new generation of composite materials.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research consist of manufacturing process and tribological properties measurement for aluminum alloy based composites, reinforced by skeleton ceramic structures. The three various materials were used for manufacturing of spatial reinforcement. There were aluminum oxide, glassy carbon and aluminum oxide covered by glassy carbon layer. Each presented reinforcement material is an own product of authors' work team. The aluminum oxide foam was produced using gel casting method [18]. This process based on sintering of foamed suspensions of $\alpha-Al_2O_3$. The second type of material was an amorphous form of carbon obtained in a process of pyrolysis of polyurethane foam with phenolic resin layer at 1000°C. This specific form of carbon materials are named glassy carbon. The last type of reinforcement was heterophases- aluminum oxide foam with glassy carbon layer. This material are created based on alumina foam obtained in gel casting method. The carbon layer was deposited of furfuryl polyalcohol used as a liquid precursor, and carbonised at 1000°C for obtaining glassy carbon.

The next step of technology consist of infiltration of various reinforcement by liquid metal. The aluminum alloy AlMg5 was used as a matrix. This process was performed in the Degussa press at 740 °C with 3 MPa of pressure. For manufactured materials, microstructures observations were

performed using Scanning Electron Microscope Hitachi S-3400N, with 25 kV of voltage in secondary electron technique.

Next, the description of tribological parameters of manufactured homo- and heterophases composites were made using pin-on-disc tribotester with 0.05 m/s of sliding speed, 2.5 MPa of load on the distance 90 m. The counterpart was a the typical sliding material - cast iron GJL-300. The friction coefficient value, its stabilisation and wear level were noted as a main friction parameters. Moreover, the wear track areas were analysed using scanning electron microscope for describing the predominant wear mechanism.

3 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The manufactured process of reinforcement foams were complex and needed an analysis of influence of various factors, like precursor viscosity, temperature of process, etc. The basic problem during production was a porosity level, especially for carbon materials. The level of porosity define finally amount of reinforcement in material. Moreover, the obtained pores of spatial reinforcement cannot be closed because it is obstacle for infiltration process. In case of carbon foam or carbon layer, the porosity strongly depend on viscosity of precursor. Too high viscosity led too closing of pores and to filled the spheres of alumina foam, while too low viscosity resulted in unequal distribution of reinforcement phase in the volume of material. Many conducted tests gave an possibility of creation of foams with required stereological parameters. The porosity of aluminum oxide foam was about 85%, what means that finally amount of reinforcement was 15% for material with Al₂O₃ foam. The deposition of carbon layer on the ceramic foam resulted in decreasing of porosity up to 80%, what gave a finally reinforcement amount near the level 20%. The case of foam made of carbon only, the porosity mainly depend on initial precursor porosity. In presented research the polyurethane foam was characterized by 60 pores per inch. This material, after infiltration by phenolic resin revealed porosity on the level about 85%. This result was similar like for Al₂O₃+GC foam. In all types of reinforcement, the closing of pores was avoided due to adequate viscosity of used resin. High porosity of spatial structure gave an opportunity to infiltration by liquid metal and to produce composite with required level of reinforcement.

Figure 1: The microstructures of manufactured composites with Al₂O₃ (a), GC (b) and Al₂O₃+GC (c) reinforcement, SEM

The microstructures of manufactured materials are presented in the figure 1. The infiltration pressure was matched to the lowest value of compressive strength of analysed foams – carbon foam. The maximum expected compressive strength of this material was between 3 – 5 MPa. The aluminum oxide foam was proper infiltrated by liquid metal (Fig. 1a). Any materials defects like porosity or areas totally closed were observed. Also proper bonding between metal and ceramic phases was obtain. In case of composite with carbon reinforcement, some defects were detected (Fig. 1b). First of them was problem on the boundaries between matrix and reinforcement phase. Due to low wettability of carbon structure by liquid metal, this areas were a privileged place for pores creation. Moreover, some small areas between walls of spatial structure were not infiltrated by metal. Those phenomena led to creation opened pores on the surface of material. The composite with heterophases reinforcement (Al₂O₃+GC) was not revealed as high problems with porosity as composite with carbon foam (Fig. 1c). In this case only slight porosity can be noted near the boundary between alumina and carbon phases. However,

for all manufactured composites a uniform distribution of reinforcement in whole volume of composite was discovered. The presence of adequate value of reinforcement on the surface should ensure required mechanical and tribological properties.

The tribological tests for composites were carried out under friction in air conditions. The obtained curves of friction coefficient (COF) in dependence on the sliding distance are presented in the figure 2a. The composite with aluminum oxide foam revealed unstable COF value at analysed distance. In the beginning part, the friction was quite low (near 0.24) then, after 30m the COF was increasing up to 0.4 in short period of time. This specific behaviour of this material in friction conditions depend on presence of ceramic phase in the area of friction surface. In part with low COF value, the main meaning of friction played a matrix. The predominant wear mechanism for aluminum matrix was plastic deformation (Fig. 3a). Still removing of the external layer of material resulted in increasing of active participation of alumina foam in friction. It resulted in COF increasing with stabilisation decreasing simultaneously. The rapid wearing of external part of material was confirmed by high mass loss (Fig. 2b).

Figures 2: The results of tribological investigations: coefficient of friction on analysed distance (a) and mass loss of material and counterpart (b)

Figures 3: The areas after friction for composites reinforced by Al₂O₃ (a), GC (b) and Al₂O₃+GC (c) foam, SEM.

However, the highest coefficient of friction value without stabilisation was discovered for composite reinforced by carbon foam (Fig. 2a). It was unexpected result because pure glassy carbon material is characterized by very low COF value, near 0.15. The high COF value of composite with carbon should be explain by low mechanical properties of carbon foam. In presented test, the applied load was focused on small area. It resulted in exceeding of maximum compressive strength in some microareas, what led to destruction of material. In the area of friction after tribological test only plastically deformed matrix without the carbon foam was discover (Fig. 3b). It is a proof that elements broken under friction condition were removed from friction point, what was visible in high mass loss value also (Fig. 2b). Due to crushing process the carbon phase cannot be smeared on the surface and lubricating process was

limited. Moreover, this process was multiplied because of obtained porosity between foam and matrix. The defects of material prevented the effective transfer of tangential forces acting on the surface during friction. The destruction process led to unstable working conditions and required more force for moving between materials of friction couple, what resulted in high friction coefficient value.

The connection of both types of material as a hybrid reinforcement structure led to fulfilment of friction requirements. This material revealed the lowest COF value without significant disruptions during friction (Fig. 2a). The high mechanical properties caused by alumina foam with proper lubricating properties caused by glassy carbon resulted in a few times lower mass loss than for homophases materials (Fig. 2b). The analysis of friction area confirmed that aluminum oxide foam were not worn (Fig. 3c). Moreover, the crushed glassy carbon particles were not removed from the friction point, but these debris were pushed into matrix material and played active role against progressive wear (Fig. 3c). The slight mass loss obtained for this material depended mainly on wear of matrix material as a plastic deformation process, especially on the beginning period of friction.

4 SUMMARY

The presented research confirmed that a manufacturing process of high quality composite material with spatial reinforcement is possible. On the one hand, the application of skeleton reinforcement give an opportunity to fulfil many specific requirements. Between the most important of them, the uniform distribution of reinforcement phase in volume of material without any materials defects, like clusters, agglomeration or sedimentation should be noted. The high opened porosity on the required level give the possibility of infiltration process by liquid metal also. The high temperature resistance of ceramic material ensure the possibility of infiltration process by almost all metals. Moreover, a foams can be using only in required areas of material, what ensure reduction of ready-made material costs. On the other hand, the creations of foams form various materials lead to achieving the wide range of properties. Between presented reinforcement materials, the alumina foam is responsible for the increase of mechanic properties. Because of high compressive strength of alumina foam, the application of final product in high loaded friction point is possible. The glassy carbon in form of layer or foam decide about tribological properties. Despite the fact of low COF value and low wear, due to GC application, the lubricant in form of oil can be avoided also. It is in accordance with natural environment protecting as a result of limitation of pollution. The hybrid connection (Al_2O_3+GC) allow to reduce of material wearing and decreasing of COF value. The synergic actions of each components lead to manufacturing of composite with unique properties. Not insignificant is a material of matrix. In presented research aluminum matrix ensure plasticity and high thermal conductivity of composite. Moreover, a low density of aluminum alloys resulted in the finally mass decreasing. Due to application of heterophase reinforcement in an aluminum matrix, a strict requirements of automotive industry in a sector of sliding materials were achieved.

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